

Synthesis of Possible Antiamoebic Agents

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Synthesis of 1-(3', 4'-dimethoxy phenyl)-1-alkyl amino heaanes were prepared for testing their activity against *Entamoeba histolytica*. Among the compounds prepared N-aryl compound was found to be most active.

OBSERVATION of high amoebicidal activity^{1,2} among a number of phenyl alkyl amines prompted us to prepare and investigate several secondary and tertiary amines of the type I. 3,4-Dimethoxy phenyl *n*-amyl ketone¹, was subjected to

reductive amination in presence of ammonia to yield 1-(3', 4'-dimethoxy phenyl) 1-amino *n*-hexane. The acylated amine on reduction with LAH in ether yielded secondary amines (I; R = H; R' = alkyl). Methylation of the secondary amines with formic acid and formaldehyde³ yielded the desired tertiary amines (I; R = Me, R' = alkyl).

Amoebicidal test report¹

In vitro amoebicidal (*Entamoeba histolytica*) testing was done at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. Amoebicidal activity has been reported in Tables 2 and 3.

Experimental

1-(3', 4'-Dimethoxy phenyl) 1-amino-*n*-hexane (I; R = R' = H): A mixture of 3,4-dimethoxy phenyl amyl ketone (47.2 g, 0.2 mol), anhydrous ammonia in absolute alcohol (300 ml., 10%) and Raney Nickel (3 tea spoonful) was hydrogenated at 150° and 120 atmosphere under stirring in an autoclave for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the catalyst filtered out. Alcohol was removed by distillation and the residual mass extracted with dil. HCl. The acid solution on basification with alkali liberated the amine which was extracted with benzene. Benzene layer was washed with water, dried over Na₂SO₄ (anhydrous) and subsequently distilled to yield the amine. It distilled as a colourless liquid b.p. 180/3 mm; yield 70% (33 g.). Picrate, m.p. 133, hydro-

chloride, m.p. 233°, recrystallised from ethyl acetate and absolute alcohol.

Acylation of the amine (I; R = R' = H): Acylation of the amine was effected with Ac₂O in the usual manner. Other acylated compounds were prepared by the interaction of the amine (I; R = R' = H; 0.03 mol.) with acid chloride (0.04 mol.) in presence of pyridine (0.05 mol.) and dry benzene (50 ml) at 10°-15° under stirring. After 1 hr, the reaction mixture was washed with dil. HCl and dil. NaOH solution successively. The benzene solution was then dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and distilled. Amides crystallised from pet. ether (60°-80°). Data shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—3,4-DIMETHOXYPHENYL-CH(NH.COR).C₅H₁₁

R	M.P.°C	Formula	N %	
			Calc.	Found
Me	70	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ O ₂ N	5.03	4.54
Et	79	C ₁₇ H ₂₇ O ₂ N	4.78	5.15
Pr	81	C ₁₈ H ₂₉ O ₂ N	4.57	4.32
Bu	84	C ₁₉ H ₃₁ O ₂ N	4.37	4.15
Am	64	C ₂₀ H ₃₃ O ₂ N	4.18	3.77

1-(3', 4'-Dimethoxy phenyl) 1-*N*-alkyl amino *n*-hexane (I; R = H; R' = alkyl) LAH (0.02 mol) was suspended in dry ether (150 ml.) and the amide (0.02 mol., dissolved in dry ether 50 ml.) enlisted in Table 1, was added slowly. The mixture was then refluxed for about 50 hr, the mass was cooled, excess of LiAlH₄ was decomposed by the dropwise addition of water, ethereal solution was filtered and the amine extracted with dil. HCl. The acid layer was basified, extracted with benzene, the benzene layer dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and distilled. Data of the amines are listed in Table 2. Hydrochloride were crystallised from water.

1-(3', 4'-Dimethoxy phenyl)-1-*N*-methyl-*N*-alkyl-amino-*n*-hexane (I; R = Me; R' = alkyl): A mixture of the above secondary amine (0.02 mol), formic acid (90%, 0.2 mol.) and formalin (0.06 mol) was

TABLE 2—3,4-DIMETHOXYPHENYL-CH(NHR).C₅H₁₁

R	B.P.(mm), °C	M.P. of Hydrochloride °C	Formula (Hydrochloride)	N%		Activity
				Calc.	Found	
Et	145(6)	127	C ₁₆ H ₂₈ O ₂ NCl	4.63	4.22	1 : 1000
Pr	150(2)	97	C ₁₇ H ₃₀ O ₂ NCl	4.43	4.60	1 : 1000
Bu	160(3)	152	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂ NCl	4.24	4.07	1 : 1000
Am	145(0.6)	157	C ₁₉ H ₃₄ O ₂ NCl	4.10	4.59	1 : 1600
Hex	135(0.4)	150	C ₂₀ H ₃₆ O ₂ NCl	3.90	4.01	1 : 4000

Emetine hydrochloride was active at 1 : 1,60,000.

heated at 90°–100° for 8 hr. The mixture was cooled, 10 ml. of 4*N*. HCl was added to it and eva-

porated to dryness on a boiling waterbath under reduced pressure. The residual mass was then treated with NaOH solution (10 ml., 10*N*) and the liberated base was extracted with benzene. The solvent layer was dried over anhydrous K₂CO₃ and distilled. Data are listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3—3,4-DIMETHOXYPHENYL-CH(NMeR').C₅H₁₁

R'	B.P.(mm), °C	Formula	N %		Activity
			Calc.	Found	
Me	150(1)	C ₁₆ H ₂₇ O ₂ N	5.29	5.18	inactive
Et	130(5)	C ₁₇ H ₂₉ O ₂ N	5.02	4.98	1 : 8000
Pr	130(2)	C ₁₈ H ₃₁ O ₂ N	4.77	4.52	1 : 8000
Bu	148(0.8)	C ₁₉ H ₃₃ O ₂ N	4.56	4.38	inactive
Am	164(4)	C ₂₀ H ₃₅ O ₂ N	4.36	4.21	1 : 8000
Hex	175(4)	C ₂₁ H ₃₇ O ₂ N	4.18	3.92	1 : 1000

Emetine hydrochloride was active at 1 : 1,60000.

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References

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